

Disinfection of Disposable N95 Respirators: A Timely Review

Michael K Gilson^{1*}, Jesse Jokerst², Shiv Patel³, Preetham Suresh⁴, Shelley Halpain⁵

May 4, 2020

1: Skaggs School of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 9500 Gilman Drive, MC 0751, UC San Diego, La Jolla, CA 92093-0751

2: Departments of NanoEngineering and Radiology, UC San Diego La Jolla, CA 92093-0448

3: UC San Diego School of Medicine Simulation Training Center, La Jolla, CA 92093-0606

4: Department of Anesthesiology and School of Medicine, 9500 Gilman Drive, MC 0606, UC San Diego, La Jolla, CA 92093-060

5: Division of Biological Sciences, Section of Neurobiology, University of California San Diego; and Sanford Consortium for Regenerative Medicine, 2800 Torrey Pines Scenic Dr., La Jolla, CA 92037

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3814217

*To whom correspondence should be addressed: mgilson@health.ucsd.edu

Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic has led to a shortage of disposable N95 filtering facepiece respirators (masks), essential items of personal protective equipment for this respiratory disease. Many health care providers are therefore considering whether to stretch their limited supply through disinfection and reuse. However, N95 face masks are not designed for reuse, so it is important to consider the advisability of this path and critically assess the various disinfection methods that have been put forward. Here, we offer a timely review of the rapidly evolving body of information on the disinfection and reuse of disposable N95 respirators. Although several candidate methods may be set aside entirely because they damage the ability of the mask to perform its intended functions, others have unique sets of advantages and disadvantages that may justify their selection depending on circumstances. In addition, there are considerations that apply equally to all methods. We would emphasize the importance of continuing to monitor the rapidly evolving literature in this area, and suggest several relatively authoritative resources to facilitate this.

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has led to over 1 million cases and 60,000 deaths in the span of 3 months in the United States alone (1), and these numbers are bound to increase over the next few months. The high pace of its spread has stressed the healthcare systems of many countries and led to shortages of critical personal protective equipment (PPE), including disposable N95 filtering facepiece respirators (FFRs). As previously anticipated by public health personnel and scientists planning to deal with future pandemics (2), the demand for N95 masks has at times outpaced supply, leading to shortages. As a consequence, many healthcare workers and administrators have considered reusing their limited supplies (3). This concept is not novel: according to the CDC, “FFR decontamination and reuse may need to be considered as a crisis capacity strategy to ensure continued availability.”(4). Moreover, recognizing the potential for influenza or Sudden Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS) pandemics to create global PPE shortages, the

National Academies of Science published guidelines for the reuse of N95 respirators and other PPE, and recommended that targeted research address methods for their safe and effective decontamination. Thus, methods for FFR decontamination and safe reuse have been under consideration for many years, as further cited below.

An ideal disinfection method for N95 respirators will

- Preserve >95% efficiency of the filtration material per specification
- Preserve easy air flow through the filtration material
- Preserve structural integrity of the mask, thus enabling user fit and elasticity of the straps
- Fully inactivate SARS-CoV-2 virus
- Kill other potential pathogens
- Avoid introducing toxic chemical residues
- Involve minimal setup and logistics (e.g. establishment of facilities, transport, working with toxic substances)
- Allow multiple safe and effective cycles of disinfection and reuse
- Minimize requirements for prohibitively expensive equipment and consumables

No method is likely to be ideal in all circumstances, and indeed one of the leading manufacturers of N95 FFRs, 3M, stated in March 2020 that they did not “recommend or support attempts to sanitize, disinfect, or sterilize 3M FFRs.”(5). However, presumably due to intense interest from the health care community, 3M reported in April 2020 that they are carrying out their own studies of disinfections methods that have been discussed in the literature or elsewhere, and provided their results to date(6). Note that their studies address only the effects of these methods on filtration and fit, and not their effectiveness at inactivating SARS-CoV-2 or other pathogens.

Whether or not disinfection should be done and what methods are most suitable will depend on institutional issues, such as availability of budget and personnel, and on scientific and clinical assessments of the available data. They also depend on the purpose: in some settings, the goal may be complete sterilization of respirators; in another, robust inactivation of SARS-CoV-2 and most other microorganisms without full sterilization may suffice. Note that not all disinfection methods considered here have been tested specifically for SARS-CoV-2 on N95s. Instead, some have used surrogate organisms or viruses or have looked at inactivation of SARS-CoV-2 on other surfaces or in aqueous medium.

A consideration that applies to all disinfection methods is that the mechanical durability of disposable N95 respirators sets an upper limit on how many cycles of disinfection and reuse should be allowed, independent of the choice of disinfection method. Thus, the risk of substandard filter performance was found to rise as N95s were donned, worn briefly, and then doffed, multiple times, *without* a disinfection step (7). Although these data are noisy, a possible recommendation from this study would be to use a given N95 respirator no more than five times. Moreover, because the duration of each use is likely longer in the clinical setting than in this study’s laboratory setting, a more conservative limit of e.g. 2-3 uses should perhaps be applied. That said, in many settings an imperfect N95 respirator may still give better protection than the available alternative.

It is also worth noting that some disinfection methods cause a gradual, often exponential(8), decline in active virus titers over time. For these methods, a treatment duration that is adequate for most cases

may not suffice for a heavily contaminated mask. Wearing a face shield along with an N95 respirator should help to reduce the degree of contamination and thus avoid excessive levels of contamination. It is also advisable to discard masks that are soiled with bodily fluids, as well as with make-up or lotions, as these materials may affect filtration properties and/or protect virus particles from some disinfectants, such as vaporized hydrogen peroxide.

The following sections offer a timely, critical review of some of the disinfection methods that have received most attention in the literature. However, this document should not be regarded as making any specific recommendations. Anyone considering adopting a method to disinfect N95 respirators should carry out their own independent analysis and assessment of which, if any, method is safest and most effective, in general and in their particular circumstances.

Dry Heating of N95s

Most or all N95 respirators use electrostatically charged polypropylene filters. Most, but not all, studies so far indicate that this material is stable to heating at 70-75 C and perhaps higher, according to multiple studies, as now summarized.

1. Stanford University and 4C Air heated this filter material for up to 20 cycles of 30 min/cycle at 75°C. Filtration efficiency and pressure drop (which measures ease of air flow through the material) were maintained for 15 and, arguably, all 20 heating cycles (Table 1)(9).
2. Another study from 4C air(10) similarly reported stable filter function after 50 30-minute cycles of disinfection at 75°C in dry conditions, and also after 50 cycles at 85°C and 30% relative humidity.
3. An earlier study that tested the effect of dry heat on filtration efficiency reported that six models of filter remained within specifications after heating for an hour at up to 100°C(11).
4. A document from the University of Tennessee Research Foundation reports negligible loss in filtration efficiency following heating at 70°C for 24 hours(12).
5. Our own internal study showed that 30 minutes at 70°C led to no apparent change in appearance, feel, or smell of two models of N95, and no loss of filtration efficiency as measured by a local respirator expert/service provider.
6. In contrast to the above encouraging results, another recent study reported that 3M Aura N95 masks cannot pass a fit factor test after more than two cycles of disinfection with dry heat at 70°C of apparently unspecified duration(8). The discrepancy relative to other studies might be explained by the fact that, unlike the others, this study did not test the filtration properties of excised fabric swatches, but instead used a Porta Count device to test filtration when the mask was being worn by a volunteer. Conceivably, the filter material retained its properties and the failure was due instead to mechanical issues, such as deformation of the mask or loss of elasticity of the straps.

Table 1. Measures of N95 function as a function of number of 30 min@75C heating cycles(9). Measurements done with a TSI 8130A instrument with flow rate of 32 L/min.

	Filtration Efficiency (%)	Pressure drop (Pa)
Pre-treatment (N=5)	97.4 (1.4)	8.8 (1.5)
5 cycles (N=3)	96.4 (0.4)	6.7 (0.6)
10 cycles (N=3)	97.3 (0.3)	8.0 (1.0)
15 cycles (N=3)	97.5 (0.4)	9.0 (1.7)

20 cycles (N=3)	96.0 (0.4)	8.3 (0.6)
------------------------	------------	-----------

The SARS-Cov-2 virus is inactivated by heat treatment. Virus in liquid transport medium was inactivated within 5 minutes by heating to 70°C, and within 30 minutes by heating to 56°C)(13). Similarly, heating of SARS-CoV-1 in culture medium to 67°C led to inactivation within 60 min, and heating at 75°C led to inactivation within 30 min. However, the virus was in aqueous medium in these studies and dry heating is known to be less effective at sterilization than is wet heating (i.e., pasteurization)(14). Thus, a recent study found that SARS-CoV-2 spotted onto the AOSafety N9504c N95 respirator and heated to 70°C was inactivated with a half-life of about 5 min and active titers were reduced by 4-5 orders of magnitude after 60 minutes(8). It is important to keep in mind that, although dry heating at 70-75°C for 60 minutes may reduce SARS-CoV-2 to negligible levels, it is not expected to fully sterilize a mask; i.e., other pathogens may persist. Full sterilization with dry heat, which requires 160°C for 2 hours, will destroy an N95 respirator(15).

It should be relatively straightforward to heat-treat N95 respirators in the clinical setting. A blanket-warmer that reaches 70°C or 75°C may be used, or an inexpensive laboratory oven may be purchased and placed in a suitable location. Clinicians may place their used respirators in paper bags and have them heated for e.g. 30 minutes at 70-85°C before reuse. Labels that indicate that a desired temperature has been reached (<https://bit.ly/2USUMbQ>) may be placed on each bag to confirm that heat-treatment has been completed. Each clinician may then recover his or her bag. One potential concern is that, especially in an oven with forced airflow, virus particles on masks might become airborne and vent out of the oven, leading to local contamination. It has thus been suggested that one use only ovens equipped with suitable filters(16).

Conclusion: dry heating for up to two disinfection cycles appears to be a simple, inexpensive, method of inactivating SARS-CoV-2 on N95 respirators, though it is probably not adequate for complete sterilization.

UV Irradiation of N95s

UV irradiation has been well studied(11,17–22) and was chosen by University of Nebraska Medical Center (<https://bit.ly/2R6Mg7X>) to disinfect N95 masks during the coronavirus epidemic. It should be relatively easy and inexpensive to implement, either by making use of a research campus’s cell culture and PCR workstations, which could be moved to the hospitals and clinics, or by purchasing UV lamps and setting up dedicated boxes or rooms. Although one study indicates that UV exposure can decrease the mechanical strength of the filter material and, to a lesser degree, of the elastic straps(20), the doses they used, up to 1000 mJ/cm², are considerably higher than those targeted by the University of Nebraska about 60 mJ/cm². Other studies cited above indicate that multiple makes/models of N95s retain function and fit after various doses of UV irradiation and 3M has reported favorable results with one UV decontamination system(6).

However, there is some concern about the reliability of UV, because any part of the mask that is shadowed, such as by another part of the mask, will not be disinfected. Indeed, one publication observed missed spots, particularly on the straps, which can twist unpredictably or be hidden by the filter(21). In addition, they noted that virus particles in droplets that soak into the material might be

protected from UV and thus remain infectious. Nonetheless, reuse following treatment with UV is clearly preferred to reuse without any disinfection treatment. In addition, UV should be effective at killing many other potential pathogens.

Conclusion: UV is a good option for inactivating SARS-CoV-2 on used N95 respirators, but care is needed to avoid shadowing, including ensuring exposure of both sides of the mask and positioning the straps appropriately. In addition, virus in droplets that soak into the filter or straps may be protected from inactivation.

Vaporized hydrogen peroxide to sterilize N95s

Vaporized hydrogen peroxide (VHP) can provide definitive sterilization by killing viruses, bacteria and bacterial spores, and fungi. It is used routinely to sterilize medical instruments, and was recently shown to rapidly inactivate SARS-CoV-2 on N95 respirators(8). Note that VHP is distinct from hydrogen peroxide gas plasma (HPGP) generated by e.g. a STERRAD sterilization unit, and that three treatments with HPGP has been found to degrade the filtration efficiency of several models of N95 respirator ;(10; see below). In contrast, the VHP method has been shown to preserve the function of multiple models of N95 respirator through more than two sterilization cycles (8,18,23,24). Indeed, a 2016 report by Battelle laboratories commissioned by the FDA(25) showed that filtration performance of the 3M Model 1860 N95 respirator was preserved through 50 cycles of VHP decontamination intense enough to kill bacterial spores on each cycle. However, the elastic straps became fragile after 10-30 cycles. In addition, it seems possible that virus particles trapped in dried fluids on the mask could be protected from hydrogen peroxide vapor and therefore survive VHP treatment. As a consequence, VHP may not be fully effective on a deeply soiled mask. The FDA recently approved use of the Batelle Decontamination System for VHP disinfection of non-cellulose-containing N95 respirators that are not visibly soiled, for up to 20 cycles of disinfection and reuse, during the coronavirus epidemic (<https://www.fda.gov/media/136529/download>). In addition, 3M has given positive assessments of a number of VHP disinfection methods(6). We note that companies that routinely provide services for microbial decontamination of laboratory tissue culture equipment may be able to implement temporary VPH disinfection facilities at hospitals or clinic sites.

Conclusion: Vaporized hydrogen peroxide treatment is a method of choice at UC San Diego due to its effectiveness and preservation of the filtration function of N95 respirators through many disinfection cycles. However, the need for a specialized setup and a continuing supply of concentrated H₂O₂ makes it relatively expensive and complex.

Other N95 disinfection methods

Other potential methods of disinfecting disposable N95 respirators are now considered, roughly in order of decreasing promise, based on existing data and ease of implementation.

Hydrogen peroxide gas plasma (HPGP), which is used in STERRAD sterilization equipment, was found to degrade the filtration efficiency somewhat below specification, for several, but not all, models of N95 respirator following three cycles of treatment(18,24). Prior studies reported use of STERRAD units resulted in good preservation of function with a single cycle of HPGP(11,15).). In March 2020, the FDA issued emergency guidance allowing its use for up to two cycles of sterilization, and 3M's recent report

concur(6). A caveat may be that earlier reports have termed the procedure “VHP,” but were presumably testing HPGP instead. As noted above, vaporized hydrogen peroxide (VPH) is distinct from hydrogen peroxide gas plasma (HPGP).

Moist heat is typically more effective at sterilization than is dry heat at the same temperature. Up to three cycles of heating 60° or 65°C in a sealed container with an open vessel of water at the same temperature did not damage filtration performance of two N95 models and led to strong reduction in influenza virus titers (17,19). A recent preprint suggests a simple method of heating N95 respirators to 85°C at high relative humidity and demonstrated preservation of fit and filtration through five disinfection cycles. In addition, 3M has reported positively on another moist-heat technology (6). It is hoped that this promising method will be tested soon for its ability to inactivate SARS-CoV-2.

Autoclaving (application of high pressure steam) at 121°C for 15 minutes, with a total start-to-finish cycle time of 40 minutes was, perhaps surprisingly, tolerated by three pleated-fabric models of N95 respirator through 10 disinfection cycles, while one non-pleated, rigid model failed on its first cycle(24). A prior study reported destruction of two types of N95 mask by autoclaving, but did not specify their make or model (15) Given that autoclaves provided definitive sterilization, are widely available, and require no specialized chemicals or handling, this method appears to deserve further consideration for some models of N95 respirator.

Ethylene oxide (EtO) gas, which is used for sterilization of lab equipment, preserved the physical integrity and filtration properties of multiple models of N95 mask, through three treatment cycles(18,24). It is likely that EtO will effectively inactivate SARS-CoV-2, but we are not aware of data to this effect. Note that EtO is highly toxic, so this method requires expertise and caution. Because EtO is also carcinogenic, 3M specifically recommends against use of this method(6).

Passive aging. The simplest way to reduce SARS-CoV-2 titers on an N95 respirator is to simply set aside the respirator for a period of time before reusing it. The persistence of active virus on dry surfaces has been found to depend on the type of surface. Thus, although SARS-CoV-2 spotted onto paper became undetectable within three hours, it lasted for two days on cloth, and worryingly for over seven days on the outer surface of a surgical mask(13), which is likely similar to the outer surface of a surgical N95 respirator, with its hydrophobic outer layer to protect against splashing. A study of SARS-CoV-2 on the surface of a non-surgical N95 respirator appears to show about 1 log reduction in active virus per hour in the absence of active disinfection(8). We are not aware of data on the effect of passive aging on the viability of other pathogens. Overall, although it seems that passive aging can be relied on to inactivate SARS-CoV-2, the time required for adequate reduction in titers is unpredictable, and possibly exceeds several days. Accordingly, CDC guidance for use of this “crisis capacity strategy” is for each health care worker to be provided with a minimum of five N95 masks for use in a daily rotation, with the unused masks allowed to age in breathable paper bags(4). This method is pleasingly simple and inexpensive. It can also be combined with any of the other disinfection techniques, such as UV irradiation or dry heating, if a further measure of safety is desired. It is not clear how well this method would protect against other pathogens.

Immersion in aqueous hydrogen peroxide solution for one cycle of disinfection did not appear to degrade the function of N95 masks (15,18). This method is pleasingly simple and may merit further consideration and study.

Immersion in aqueous chlorine bleach produced minor(11,15,18) to major(9,12) filter damage. The variations might result from differences in bleach concentrations or other details. Residual bleach odor also raised concerns about health risks. Given the wide availability of chlorine bleach, further study of this approach may be of value, but it is not currently considered a method of choice.

Microwave-generated steam, a method in which the N95 respirator is microwaved along with an open vessel of water, led to minor structural damage to the respirators in two studies (18,19) but not a third(17).

Immersion in 70% isopropyl alcohol (IPA) followed by drying reduces filtration efficiency(8,9,12).

Treatment of N95 masks with soap and water markedly degraded their filtration performance(12,15).

Dry heating at 160°C, a known sterilization method, also led to destruction of sample N95 respirators in less than 30 min (15).

Summary

A range of methods have been proposed to disinfect N95 FFRs. The simplest method, passive aging, is exceedingly simple to implement, appears to be a reasonable option, and is supported as a crisis measure by the CDC. Perhaps the best developed and most definitive approach, VPH, provides true sterilization and is accepted as an emergency measure by the FDA, but is relatively complex and costly. Other methods, such as UV irradiation, low temperature dry heat, and perhaps moist heat, should be faster and more effective than passive aging, but are, arguably, less definitive than VPH. The decision whether to disinfect N95 FFRs and, if so, how, must be made based on circumstances, factoring in considerations that include not only the efficacy of the method but also the available alternatives, costs, and the need for official sanction, such as FDA approval.

Because this topic is of extremely high current interest, the literature is quite dynamic. Indeed, many of the studies cited in this review are still preprints. Those interested in this topic are advised to watch for and check over the refereed articles that are likely to follow, and to actively monitor for new publications. A relatively efficient way to keep abreast of new developments is to follow key sites, such as 3M's ongoing revisions of their Technical Report on Decontamination of 3M Filtering Facepiece Respirators (<https://multimedia.3m.com/mws/media/18248690/decontamination-methods-for-3m-n95-respirators-technical-bulletin.pdf>), the N95DECON website (n95decon.org), the CDC's page on Decontamination and Reuse of Filtering Facepiece Respirators (<https://www.cdc.gov/coronavirus/2019-ncov/hcp/ppe-strategy/decontamination-reuse-respirators.html>), and the FDA's list of Emergency Use Authorizations for PPE (<https://www.fda.gov/medical-devices/emergency-situations-medical-devices/emergency-use-authorizations#covid19ppe>).

Acknowledgements and Disclosures

MKG has an equity interest in, and is a cofounder and scientific advisor of, VeraChem LLC.

References

1. COVID-19 Map [Internet]. Johns Hopkins Coronavirus Resource Center. [cited 2020 May 4]. Available from: <https://coronavirus.jhu.edu/map.html>
2. Committee on the Development of Reusable Facemasks for Use During an Influenza Pandemic, Board on Health Sciences Policy, Institute of Medicine of the National Academies. Reusability of Facemasks During an Influenza Pandemic: Facing the Flu [Internet]. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press; 2006. Available from: <https://www.nap.edu/catalog/11637/reusability-of-facemasks-during-an-influenza-pandemic-facing-the-flu>
3. Livingston E, Desai A, Berkwits M. Sourcing Personal Protective Equipment During the COVID-19 Pandemic. JAMA [Internet]. 2020 Mar 28 [cited 2020 May 4]; Available from: <https://jamanetwork.com/journals/jama/fullarticle/2764031>
4. COVID-19 Decontamination and Reuse of Filtering Facepiece Respirators | CDC [Internet]. [cited 2020 Apr 2]. Available from: <https://www.cdc.gov/coronavirus/2019-ncov/hcp/ppe-strategy/decontamination-reuse-respirators.html>
5. 3M Company. Technical Bulletin: Disinfection of Filtering Facepiece Respirators. 2020 Mar.
6. 3M Company. Technical Bulletin: Disinfection of Filtering Facepiece Respirators. 2020 Apr.
7. Bergman MS, Viscusi DJ, Zhuang Z, Palmiero AJ, Powell JB, Shaffer RE. Impact of multiple consecutive donnings on filtering facepiece respirator fit. Am J Infect Control. 2012 May 1;40(4):375–80.
8. Fischer R, Morris DH, Doremalen N van, Sarchette S, Matson J, Bushmaker T, et al. Assessment of N95 respirator decontamination and re-use for SARS-CoV-2. medRxiv. 2020 Apr 15;2020.04.11.20062018.
9. mask-ppe-EBM-v1.3-3-25-20.pdf | Powered by Box [Internet]. [cited 2020 Apr 2]. Available from: <https://stanfordmedicine.app.box.com/v/covid19-PPE-1-2>
10. Liao L, Xiao W, Zhao M, Yu X, Wang H, Wang Q, et al. Can N95 respirators be reused after disinfection? And for how many times? medRxiv. 2020 Apr 17;2020.04.01.20050443.
11. Viscusi DJ, Bergman MS, Eimer BC, Shaffer RE. Evaluation of Five Decontamination Methods for Filtering Facepiece Respirators. Ann Occup Hyg. 2009 Nov 1;53(8):815–27.
12. Information and FAQs on the Performance, Protection, and Sterilization of Face Mask Materials [Internet]. University of Tennessee Research Foundation. 2020 [cited 2020 Apr 2]. Available from: <https://utrf.tennessee.edu/information-faqs-performance-protection-sterilization-of-face-mask-materials/>
13. Chin A, Chu J, Perera M, Hui K, Yen H-L, Chan M, et al. Stability of SARS-CoV-2 in different environmental conditions. medRxiv. 2020 Mar 27;2020.03.15.20036673.
14. Pasteurization. In: Wikipedia [Internet]. 2020 [cited 2020 Apr 2]. Available from: <https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Pasteurization&oldid=948518173>

15. Viscusi D, King W, Shaffer R. Effect of decontamination on the filtration efficiency of two filtering facepiece respirator models. *J Int Soc Respir Prot.* 2007;24:93–107.
16. Dry Heat Ovens Can Effectively Disinfect N95 Masks | [Internet]. SBU News. 2020 [cited 2020 May 4]. Available from: https://news.stonybrook.edu/sb_medicine/dry-heat-ovens-can-effectively-disinfect-n95-masks/
17. Lore MB, Heimbuch BK, Brown TL, Wander JD, Hinrichs SH. Effectiveness of Three Decontamination Treatments against Influenza Virus Applied to Filtering Facepiece Respirators. *Ann Occup Hyg.* 2012 Jan 1;56(1):92–101.
18. Bergman MS, Viscusi DJ, Heimbuch BK, Wander DJD, Sambol AR, Shaffer DRE. Evaluation of Multiple (3-Cycle) Decontamination Processing for Filtering Facepiece Respirators: *J Eng Fibers Fabr* [Internet]. 2010 Dec 1 [cited 2020 Apr 2]; Available from: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/155892501000500405>
19. Heimbuch BK, Wallace WH, Kinney K, Lumley AE, Wu C-Y, Woo M-H, et al. A pandemic influenza preparedness study: use of energetic methods to decontaminate filtering facepiece respirators contaminated with H1N1 aerosols and droplets. *Am J Infect Control.* 2011 Feb;39(1):e1-9.
20. Lindsley WG, Martin SB, Thewlis RE, Sarkisian K, Nwoko JO, Mead KR, et al. Effects of Ultraviolet Germicidal Irradiation (UVGI) on N95 Respirator Filtration Performance and Structural Integrity. *J Occup Environ Hyg.* 2015;12(8):509–17.
21. Mills D, Harnish DA, Lawrence C, Sandoval-Powers M, Heimbuch BK. Ultraviolet germicidal irradiation of influenza-contaminated N95 filtering facepiece respirators. *Am J Infect Control.* 2018 Jul 1;46(7):e49–55.
22. ARA Research to Mitigate a Shortage of Respiratory Protection Devices During Public Health Emergencies | www.ara.com [Internet]. [cited 2020 Apr 2]. Available from: <https://www.ara.com/news/ara-research-mitigate-shortage-respiratory-protection-devices-during-public-health-emergencies>
23. Kenney P, Chan BK, Kortright K, Cintron M, Havill N, Russi M, et al. Hydrogen Peroxide Vapor sterilization of N95 respirators for reuse. *medRxiv.* 2020 Mar 27;2020.03.24.20041087.
24. Kumar A, Kasloff SB, Leung A, Cutts T, Strong JE, Hills K, et al. N95 Mask Decontamination using Standard Hospital Sterilization Technologies. *medRxiv.* 2020 Apr 20;2020.04.05.20049346.
25. Battelle, Columbus, OH 43201. Final Report for the Bioquell Hydrogen Peroxide Vapor (HPV) Decontamination for Reuse of N95 Respirators (Study Number 3245) [Internet]. 2016 [cited 2020 Apr 5]. Available from: <https://www.fda.gov/media/136386/download>